

White Paper ID Number	W011
Title of White Paper	Back to the FUture: Supporting NEw Science with our Legacy Data
ID of Associated Expression of Interest	E008
Topic Area of White Paper	data analysis, data management and data storage

Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

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Back to the Future: Supporting New Science with our Legacy Data

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

We draw attention to the real danger of loss that now threatens all of our heritage data – high-quality scientific observations that have been carefully preserved for many decades. Once the CCD became the routine detector for observing, and analyses were performed electronically, the analogue data were left in their virgin forms, i.e., inaccessible to modern projects, and could not therefore be included in research even though the information that they carried might be critical to it. Almost all of our Canadian heritage data remain in that inaccessible format (as do the vast majority of astronomy’s analogue data elsewhere). Data that are inaccessible get judged as unuseable, and risk being discarded. Insofar as those risks may not be fully recognized within the Canadian community, we describe the present situation, and rehearse the steps that need to be taken in order to derive the very best astrophysics that our total data – a combination of recent and older – will enable. We appeal for community-wide support in this data rescue, and outline the dangers of continuing to do nothing.

1. The focus of this White Paper

The era of modern research has been described as the age of Big Data, and with good reason. It is also the age of big telescopes, big projects, big collaborations, and big surveys. Observational data, in quantities never encountered before and almost unthinkable in range, application and precision, will swamp our facilities, tax all our human skills to the limit, and absorb all our person-power. The scientific output is confidently expected to be revolutionary; extrapolations from what are, in comparison, rather modest projects (Hipparcos, SDSS, PTF . . .) suggest discoveries at rates that can only be described in terms of hyperbole. Once placed in the public domain, those new data will overwhelm our imaginations and gobble up all our computational energy.

Nevertheless, all the new science which will emerge from these surveys will share a very serious shortcoming: the data will be unable to penetrate back in time before (at most) about 25 years, when our data were first recorded electronically and archived. Yet a great many changes which the cosmos can manifest take place more slowly – often very much more slowly – and cannot be studied or even observed within one rather small 25-year window of digital access. Evidence of anything that is happening slowly is therefore almost totally inaccessible to us. The bias that such a limitation will build into every cosmological model derived from those modern data will represent one of the worst legacies that any generation of astronomers has ever handed down to its successors.

2. Our long-term archives: the current situation

Salvation could be within easy reach. Over the past decades and even centuries, astronomers have not only carried out observations of a plethora of different astronomical objects but they have preserved them too, so succeeding generations have inherited for free a huge legacy of historical data. The very great majority of those observations was recorded photographically, and are now stored in observatory plate stores, though often in less than ideal conditions and distributed somewhat inconveniently in some 30–40 different sites and in different countries around the world. But those are the very records that contain much-needed information about long-term changes in our Universe, and although they are in *analogue* formats such as glass plates, primitive magnetic tapes, graphs, charts and observing log-books, it is incumbent upon the astronomical community as a whole to ensure that they are made fully accessible for research.

We may well ask why astronomy's legacy data are not already accessible and in regular use. The short answer is that their analogue formats prevent the ready access required by modern research, and it requires some effort and resources to make them fully accessible. The nature of the media on which they were recorded means that a separate stage of preliminary interpretation – that of transforming from an analogue to a digital mode – has to be introduced, necessarily absorbing time, resources, equipment (mostly custom-built), training – and dedication. Although the means to carry out those transformations correctly have been understood thoroughly since first explained by the 19th-century photographic scientists F. Hurter and V.C. Driffield, who introduced, and explained, methods of quantitative measurements using photographic emulsions, to date rather few of our plate archives have been converted to the electronic formats that all modern research requires. (A notable exception is the major collection at Harvard College Observatory, outlined in Section 6A). Of the non-photographic materials in astronomy's archives, a small number are hand-written papers, some are paper-chart recordings, and a few are primitive magnetic tapes with 'foreign' formats (i.e., not described, or unrecognized) and for which there are hardly any tape-reading machines now.

In addition to images and spectra of stars and galaxies, astronomy also possesses valuable collections of observations of the Sun – many through selected filters, to follow (for instance) the development of flares or faculae – plus collections of Solar System objects and observations of comets and meteors as well. In addition, NRC Canada in Ottawa hosts numerous large-format spectra of laboratory molecules which were observed and recorded by Gerhard Herzberg. Many of those molecules will not previously have been studied spectroscopically, and there is a real possibility that the sets record some of the compounds responsible for the diffuse interstellar bands. The plates have never been digitized; it would be an excellent project for students, provided one could identify the best scanner(s) for the purpose.

Furthermore, numerous observers and observatories still hold data on less ancient (e.g., 9-track) magnetic tapes, DAT tapes and other 'digital' media that pre-dated born-digital observing. Observers who worked at the DAO or the CFHT, and surely elsewhere too, are among those who stand to lose their data permanently unless means can be recovered to read the tapes and rescue the data while suitable software (e.g., that created by the observer) can still be identified and applied.

Despite the fact that those heritage data are vital for understanding some of the many changes that can be detected in the universe, they have a desperately uncertain future. Unless or until the photographic plates *and the associated logbook records* have been digitized and correctly processed, and the originals also preserved, our hopes for broadening our understanding of the changing nature of the cosmos must rest on the precarious analogue materials themselves, and those are degrading – slowly but surely. Glass plates are always at risk of damage (breaking, cracking or scratches), and of complete loss through flood or fire. Even those in nominally good storage places in Canada are at increasing risk of becoming degraded and thence totally lost. A more insidious fate is also shadowing all plate stores: that of human ignorance; if lack of sufficiently frequent use gets interpreted as lack of interest by the community, there is a very real danger that a whole archive will be discarded as "no longer of interest".

3. A closer look at photographic observations

In broad terms, there are two types of photographic observations: direct images, and spectra. (Objective-prism plates, bearing spectra at the low resolution described as "classification resolution", can be included with direct images for the purposes of this White Paper). Images come in an enormous assortment of sizes, resolutions and depths. Those of the best quality, mostly produced for astrometric purposes, require correspondingly high-class treatment, for they will reveal minuscule changes of brightness or position that can be combined with data from *Gaia* in order to define

long-term orbits and long-term characteristics, particularly of NEOs or comets. Yet even images of rather low-quality (small format, very grainy emulsions and/or with no photometric information) can contribute important information, e.g., as to whether an object was visible or changing at the time the plate was taken. Spectra, on the other hand, demand, and must be given, the correct treatment regardless of apparent quality, or the information which they bear will be rendered somewhat useless (except for discerning qualitatively whether a star was eclipsing, say, or was flaring in $H\alpha$).

4. The danger of continuing to do nothing

The problem is actually becoming more acute than corresponds to the natural degradation caused by ageing. We do not always find phenomena representing change only among the faintest or the most distant; many of the objects less faint than those currently being monitored by routine surveys from both space and the ground exhibit changes that have not yet been investigated with enough thoroughness to understand the physics that is driving the changes. Eclipsing stars that exhibit evidence of “chromospheric eclipses”, for example, represent a wealth of unique science that has certainly not been processed at all exhaustively, leaving our models of stars with an incomplete treatment of the outermost layers through which all of a star’s radiation passes. It is handy to apply generalized rules to the formation of metallic-line stars, but how many exceptions to the rule have been swept under the carpet for convenience? How many apparent binary stars in the Galaxy are in fact multiple systems, and how much of the theoretical missing mass of the Galaxy do they contain between them?

Examples like these can be tackled by appealing to data that span a sufficiently wide time-base. They are just the very tip of a much deeper edifice of examples in astrophysics where more emphasis and resources are needed, and where historical data can play a deciding role, for instance in recognizing period modulations that suggest a third body in a binary system, or distinguishing the transient from the quasi-permanent features or characteristics of a long-period system. Even more importantly, we cannot foretell what directions our science will take in (even the near) the future, and astrophysics will not stand still while we wait to lengthen the time-base of our digital archives. Nor is there any way of recapturing one-off events of immense significance from the distant past unless we can make use of our archives. The price we have to pay for this extension to our present scientific knowledge is that of making a single, lasting effort to rescue our heritage analogue data, and by comparison to other modern projects it is a very modest price.

For an age that was born surrounded by things digital, it is essential to retain close links with remaining knowledge and expertise about how to handle photographic plates correctly, how to understand and extract photometry and spectrophotometry accurately, and how to understand the associated errors and biases. That expertise is almost exclusively lodged with people who were active in research *before* the introduction of digital detectors, most of whom are now retired or are becoming lost to astronomy altogether. Time is therefore getting frighteningly short for executing these data rescues, and the rate of that shortening is accelerating. Ironically, carrying out digitization projects is not expensive in relation to the big spends on the new telescopes of today; most plate collections need the use of purpose-built equipment, but modern prototype examples of such equipment, or upgraded versions of older machines, are now in use and can be cloned relatively cheaply for export elsewhere. Trained manpower will be a dominant expense, but that requirement is not exclusive to plate scanning.

A comprehensive programme to digitize analogue materials correctly requires informed choices, specialized equipment and human skills that are rapidly disappearing. There are obvious roles here for volunteers and citizen scientists; volunteers can write specified entries from images of plate envelopes into text files, the proof-reading being performed by duplicating the effort several times

and checking for differences. Classification of spectra for outline cataloguing can be carried out by citizen scientists, particularly those who are experienced in taking their own spectra. Furthermore, the scientific and cultural histories associated with old data and respective practices constitutes excellent stories of history to share with the public and with most layman levels of science.

Canada can play a supremely important role here as exemplar: by digitizing its photographic heritage, by incorporating the outputs into research that becomes published, and by acting as a role model for all other observatories. The DAO (Victoria) already has two custom-designed scanning "PDS" microdensitometers that were built in the 1980s expressly for digitizing photographic plates. The technology is well understood and the methods of application can be taught. All that is preventing a full-scale digitization programme is lack of funds to operate those machines and carry out preliminary data reductions. It seems a small price to pay for the rescue of our astronomical heritage.

5. Does it really require special equipment?

Commercial flat-bed scanners, nowadays fairly ubiquitous for clerical and office jobs, are sometimes adopted as a quick solution for scanning plates; they are readily available, inexpensive, simple to operate, and easy to replace if malfunctioning. But there are serious drawbacks. Many lack the physical rigidity and dimensional stability of a conventional microphotometer; some of the inherent lack of precision can be countered by scanning each object a second time after rotation through 90° , though that half defeats the argument of the superior speed which such an instrument offers. The most serious disadvantage (and which is particularly acute in the case of spectrograms) is the way the incident light that illuminates the sample is scattered. Most commercial scanners use a bright light for that illuminating. But a photographic emulsion is rough (that was how we used to distinguish in the dark which side of a glass plate was its sensitive one!), so any light that falls upon an element of emulsion from a direction other than strictly normal will be included in the total intensity of light transmitted by the element in question. The scale of the intensities in the original will therefore be vitiated. In actual fact this is an excusable fault, since flat-bed scanners were not designed to deal with scientific photographic negatives; they were invented for, and are extensively used for, scanning documents, the objective being to produce a copy of the original with a digital device, and it does not require the image to be perfectly faithful in either position or photometry, provided it is suitably close enough to the original.

The major problem with a flat-bed scanner derives from a need for speed. Copying sheets of paper – usually A4 in size, or near that – requires a system that is capable of creating a digital image rapidly of a large field of view, rather than scanning serially from one element to the next. A number of commercial scanners incorporate software that softens the edges of sharp images "to give a more pleasing appearance", thus losing vital astronomical information. It is not possible to model the scattering (in order to subtract it digitally from the scanned image) because – particularly in the case of a spectrum – the pattern and the amount of scattering will be governed by the local nature of the exposure (chiefly its density of lines), and that will be different at every different position across the plate. If the output from such a scanner is thus unreliable, it reduced to nought all the value of having spent resources for decades on the maintenance of so many plate archives, and in addition it threatens to discredit the intrinsic value of the historical data. This is a serious matter; all the basics of astrophysics were founded upon a century of photographic observations, and it will not behove our science if widespread doubts are cast upon the quality of those founding data simply because a method to scan them is not being applied optimally.

Exceptions to that rather draconian statement can sometimes be justified, but should only be adopted if the same results are obtained on samples that have also been digitized with machines that were purpose-built for scanning photographic plates. A flat-bed scanner is valuable for making

quick images of logbook pages, or of plate envelopes, so that one can build an inventory of a plate archive without needing to visit it in person or disturb plates more than can be helped. It can sometimes be used for digitizing small-format, grainy, direct plates, and also for digitizing objective-prism plates if all one wants is a qualitative plot of the SED of each star, but it should not be used where positional precision is a high need, and especially not for spectroscopy where the grey-scale implicit in the darkening of the emulsion is where all the fundamental information in the spectral line profiles is lodged. Extracting that information accurately involves measuring the blackening of the grains in each individual pixel by transmitting through each step a beam of light so narrow that all the rest of the plate is shielded from it.

6. New science from digitized plates

(A) The *DASCH* project at Harvard

What has been achieved through an intense, 5-year dedicated programme at Harvard is a superb example of the richness that historical archives of data are potentially able to offer astrophysics. The Harvard project, *DASCH* (the Digital Access to a Sky Century at Harvard), set itself the goal of scanning in 5 years its entire collection of 500,000 large-format (10 × 8 inch) glass plates containing images of both the northern and the southern sky and dating back over a century. A purpose-designed high-speed scanner, together with software to manage the whole procedure, was funded through grants from the NSF and other sources and is operated by a small team of trained and dedicated staff and specialists. The project is now nearing completion, and has shown to the world innumerable newly-identified variable stars, provided input for time-domain studies on time-scales embracing weeks to decades, given light-curves of novæ and other transient objects, and many more, and most were unexpected – a characteristic and attractive feature of archival work. The long time-base of *DASCH*, combined with the relatively rapid cadence of the observations, is proving of unique value for setting time-constraints on many of the classes of variables and transients that have been detected, and has already given rise to a large number of publications. The project has also detected and measured historical outbursts of black-hole low-mass X-ray binaries – objects which flare in B- and optical bands through some 5–10 magnitudes. In the rare cases of repeating outbursts the time-scales can be substantial – of the order of 30–100 years. Successes by *DASCH* at identifying these anomalous objects has increased as much as 10-fold the number previously known, and has also enabled the status of similar kinds of objects to be identified correctly.

Other plate archives may not have the richness, size and quality of Harvard's, but each nevertheless has something unique – data from a special programme, or (maybe) the chance to supply data that are missing from some other collection (even the Harvard set has an infamous 'Menzel gap' from ~1955 to 1970 when the then Director, Donald Menzel, withdrew financial support from the observing stations and effectively stopped the plates series for about 15 years. The Harvard team is hoping that other plate collections will eventually be able to supply acceptable observations of the relevant regions to fill in the data that are currently lacking.

(B) The spectroscopic legacy of the DAO

In contrast, the plate archives of the Dominion Astrophysical Observatory hold almost exclusively spectra (and number over 100,000). The logbooks of both the 1.8-m and the 1.2-m telescopes have been digitized, and can be searched through the CADC Website (www.cadc-ccda.hia-ihp.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/cadcbn). At the turn of the century Lick Observatory (CA) was using its 36-inch refractor to measure stellar radial velocities, and publishing the results. J.S. Plaskett, the founder and first Director of the DAO, determined that the DAO's newly-minted 72-inch, which already carried a Cassegrain spectrograph, should also be dedicated to the determination and analysis of stellar radial

velocities, and that he would commence with the stars which had been observed at Lick and whose published values suggested variability, i.e., binarity. Observing at the DAO (Victoria) was thus dominated for many years by the Observatory's programme of determining stellar radial velocities, resulting in the determination and publication of a solid core of spectroscopic binary orbits. As a consequence, the DAO plate archive (which dates from 1917) is particularly rich in series of certain binary stars, and while most of the plates may have been measured by hand at the time, collating all the plates of a selected object and studying its radial-velocity orbit in detail may indicate whether the system contains more than two components, implying a greater total mass for the system and setting valuable constraints on stellar evolution theory.

Routine photometry or spectroscopy of stars, e.g., for cluster membership, has turned up instances of eclipses that stopped happening owing to the rotation of the orbital plane of the binary, and inviting the interesting chance that some systems might *begin* to eclipse through the same effect. This is work that could be condensed into a relatively brief span of time if archives of digitized spectra were prepared and accessible. It would be difficult (though not impossible) to establish such changes of state from recent data alone, except in cases of improbably short period.

(C) The legacy of spectrograms and direct images of the DDO

The legacy of the DDO is also impressive, and in several ways complementary to that of the DAO in Victoria. The main telescope is younger than the DAO 1.8-m by 18 years (and a smidge larger), and has given rise to an archive of over 60,000 spectra and more than 10,000 direct plates. Research at both the DAO and the DDO sites has become limited insofar as direct imaging is concerned owing to the creeping menace of city lights, but narrow-slit spectroscopy has still been able to flourish. From 1971–1997 the DDO operated a 60-cm reflector in Chile, and which has been very active in imaging (particularly of star clusters and galaxies), spectroscopy and photometry. Both observatories have supported observations of novae, CP stars and binaries or multiple systems, and have made a point of monitoring objects which manifest changes. Considerable gains can therefore be expected by digitizing selections of Canada's medium- and high-dispersion spectra and merging the results on objects in common.

(D) Elsewhere: Revolutionary results from *Carte du Ciel* plates

Applying new techniques and new data to historic observations has already produced some eye-opening facts. By way of example, we record that staff at l'Observatoire de Paris (France) have recently completed a new scanning machine, "NAROO", capable of generating accurate scans of large-scale images, including plates from the *Carte du Ciel* series. It is interesting to note how it used to be claimed that the output from *Gaia* would be so precise that contributions to an orbit from historic data would not offer much advantage. However, in revising the reductions of the original scans of their *Carte du Ciel* plates the team in Paris used *Gaia*'s newly-determined positions for the stars adopted as standards on the Paris plates, with the astonishing result that the intrinsic accuracy of the results derived from the historical set could be improved by up to a factor of 10.

(E) The larger picture

A comprehensive plan for data preservation needs to be developed in parallel with similar efforts starting up elsewhere, not only at Harvard but also at the AAVSO (which maintains an excellent archive of observations of variable stars), at KPNO (for archives of images of the Sun) and by the new project APPLAUSE (a consortium of plate collections held in Germany). Many of the latter are investigating long-term photometric brightness, and could conceivably be allied with data held by the AAVSO. None appears to be tackling spectra.

The importance and urgency of this issue was recognized by the IAU, who passed Resolution B3 at GA XXX (2018): “On Preservation, Digitization and Scientific Exploration of Historical Astronomical Data”:

recognizing that the data accumulated over the past decades and even centuries will be lost unless a concentrated action is taken to identify and preserve all significant records;

recommends that a concerted effort be made to ensure the preservation, digitization, and scientific exploration of all of astronomy’s historical data, both analogue and primitive digital, and associated records.

7. Our appeal to the Canadian community

An inventory of Canadian plates of scientific quality lists 170,000 spectra and 17,000 images from the DAO, DDO and Elginfield Observatory combined, extending across a time-base of 100 years, covering a range of scales, dispersions and wavelengths, and offering a fascinating portfolio of achievable new science. Although the DAO has upgraded its two digitizing microphotometers there is no budget for operating them. Possibilities of cloning a high-speed scanner for direct plates (such as the *DASCH* instrument) need to be discussed and negotiated once funding is assured. Astronomers can also point to numerous 9-track magnetic tapes holding data but which cannot now be read for want of a tape-reader (though a few such machines do still exist, and could be borrowed or used).

It is the duty of all who can assist – with practical experience and expertise, or assistance in raising enough funding – to help our astronomical community to rescue and re-use, in electronic formats, these unique (i.e., unrepeatable) observations. The outputs will be placed in the public domain; the benefits will be for everyone.

We hereby call upon the astronomical community in Canada to recognize the gravity of the situation, and to commit to supporting preservation and digitization efforts both locally and nationally by helping to channel adequate resources appropriately, and by prioritizing efforts where the physical condition of the heritage data so dictate. Astronomers in Canada already have much of the expertise needed, at least for digitizing spectra, and will be able to lead and teach others the methods required.

8. Summary and Statement

- *Data at Risk.* The analogue data which make up our global astronomical heritage are becoming increasingly fragile, and are at grave risk of physical loss. The data extend back in time over 100 years, and the information which they carry is both unique and irreplaceable. In addition, the expertise needed to guide and direct the correct and permanent recovery of that information in electronic formats is also becoming increasingly difficult to reach. Astronomy worldwide is thus in danger of losing the chance to consult historical data archives profitably. Canada faces the same risk, but is in a special position of being able to make positive efforts to recover valuable sub-sections of those data.

- *Anticipating new science.* It is well known that the introduction of a new technology results in new discoveries and new science. The nature of such discoveries cannot, by definition, be predicted with any accuracy, but one can be confident that any science in which the span of the time-base is of high importance will benefit from the ability to access these older data on-line in what will be, almost exclusively, the first time that such access has been available electronically. In this very real sense, astronomy will be able to go “back to the future”. For example, that concept was proven unquestionably by the successful digitization of historical spectra of the enigmatic object ϵ Aurigae (period of 27 years) and to compare them with modern observations covering its eclipse of 2010.

It was the first time that such an enrichment to observational science had been attempted, and it produced results that were both intriguing and unexpected.

- *A wide spectrum of benefits.* The benefits of this undertaking will not be restricted to pure research. There will be ample opportunities for Volunteers and citizen scientists to take part in programmes to classify objects from thumb-nail images, to join in related 'search and discovery' activities on-line, to investigate historical, cultural, political and fiscal interplay represented by patterns of data-taking, and to use copies of data for teaching and learning purposes, including public demonstrations of how data have been, and can still be, shared and re-used.
- *A strong leadership role for Canada.* Canada's role in this endeavour will be one of unrivalled leadership, and will place the operators in strong positions of teaching and role-setting. The greatest risk to this programme is being unable to raise the resources before irreparable damage occurs to the data.
- *Cost-benefit ratio.* The costs involved will be depend upon the scale of what is attempted. Training and then employing specialized workforces absorbs money, but no more so than by other astronomical projects, and maybe a little less because of significant input by volunteers in preliminary tasks like cataloguing and inventorying. For example, labour costs to digitize 50,000 high-dispersion spectra would cost of the order of \$1M. The DAO already has two upgraded scanners for digitizing spectra, and more could be obtained for operating elsewhere; the one from the DDO is in the S&T Museum in Ottawa. Special high-speed scanners could be obtained for handling direct images by cloning one already developed by Harvard, Shanghai or Paris, thus bypassing R&D costs. In terms of the new science that will be enabled, and in view of the huge amounts of telescope time already expended on producing these data in the first place, the cost-benefit ratio is reckoned as modest.
- *Education and outreach.* Working with historical data but in a modern setting offers an effective demonstration of the often overlooked fact that scientific acumen is not directly related to technological progress, and that in fact scientists of the past could show remarkable insight when they had more time to think and talk rather than being slaves to computers. There are also strong links with societal and cultural developments that paralleled – or sometimes curtailed – scientific progress; materials for technology and employment fashions and policies are two such topics.